

Acute O₂ Sensing: Role of Coenzyme QH₂/Q Ratio and Mitochondrial ROS Compartmentalization

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SUMMARY

Acute O₂ sensing by peripheral chemoreceptors is essential for mammalian homeostasis. Carotid body glomus cells contain O₂sensitive ion channels, which trigger fast adaptive cardiorespiratory reflexes in response to hypoxia. O₂sensitive cells have unique metabolic characteristics that favor the hypoxic generation of mitochondrial complex I (MCI) signaling molecules, NADH and reactive oxygen species (ROS), which modulate membrane ion channels. We show that responsiveness to hypoxia progressively disappears after inducible deletion of the *Ndufs2* gene, which encodes the 49 kDa subunit forming the coenzyme Q binding site in MCI, even in the presence of MCII substrates and chemical NAD⁺ regeneration. We also show contrasting effects of physiological hypoxia on mitochondrial ROS production (increased in the intermembrane space and decreased in the matrix) and a marked effect of succinate dehydrogenase activity on acute O₂ sensing. Our results suggest that acute responsiveness to hypoxia depends on coenzyme QH₂/Q ratio-controlled ROS production in MCI.

INTRODUCTION

Acute O₂ sensing is essential for the adaptation of mammals to changing environments and pathophysiological conditions. Decreases in blood O₂ tension (PO₂) are detected by arterial chemoreceptors, in particular those in the carotid body (CB), to trigger rapid compensatory cardiorespiratory reflexes (hyperventilation and sympathetic activation) within a few seconds. The responsiveness of the CB to a decrease in PO₂ depends on chemoreceptor, or glomus cells, which contain O₂-sensitive K⁺ channels. Closure of these channels during hypoxia causes cell depolarization and the release of transmitters that activate excitatory fibers, which terminate in the brain stem respiratory center (for a recent review see López-Barneo et al., 2016). O₂-sensitive K⁺ channels have also been reported in other physiologically relevant cell classes, such as pulmonary arterial smooth muscle or adrenal chromaffin cells (Weir et al., 2005). However, the mechanisms whereby glomus and other cells acutely sense decreases in PO₂ have remained elusive (see Peers, 2015). Rotenone, a mitochondrial complex I (MCI) blocker, occludes acute O₂ sensing by peripheral chemoreceptors (Ortega-Sáenz et al., 2003; García-Fernández et al., 2007; Thompson et al., 2007). Recently, we have shown that ablation of the *Ndufs2* gene, which encodes the 49 kDa protein at the ubiquinone/rotenone binding site of the MCI catalytic core (see Baradaran et al., 2013), in catecholaminergic (tyrosine hydroxylase-positive [TH⁺]) cells results in mice (TH-NDUFS2 mice) with selective abolition of the hypoxic ventilatory response (HVR). In addition, *Ndufs2*-deficient CB chemoreceptor cells are insensitive to hypoxia, although they show normal responses to other stimuli such as hypercapnia or hypoglycemia (Fernández-Aguera et al., 2015). Interestingly, inactivation of the *Ndufs4* gene, which encodes an MCI accessory subunit without a catalytic role, results in mice with 50% reduction in MCI activity but normal responsiveness to hypoxia of single glomus cells (Fernández-Aguera et al., 2015). Although *Ndufs2* deficiency suppresses MCI activity, glomus cells from TH-NDUFS2 mice can survive and maintain normal ATP levels and functional properties. Thus, it seems that in these cells succinate dehydrogenase

activity can support the mitochondrial electron transport chain (ETC) to permit their survival in the absence of MCI (Fernández-Aguera et al., 2015). In contrast, there is massive death of glomus cells upon genetic disruption of succinate dehydrogenase function (Platero-Luengo et al., 2014). Based on these observations, we have proposed a comprehensive model of acute O₂ sensing in which hypoxia leads to a surge of reduced pyridine nucleotides (NADH) and reactive oxygen species (ROS) in MCI, which, in turn, modulate membrane ion channels (Fernández-Aguera et al., 2015; Gao et al., 2017a).

Glomus cells from TH-NDUFS2 mice, with embryonic MCI deficiency, exhibit a marked increase in the basal levels of NADH and ROS (Fernández-Aguera et al., 2015). A cellular decrease in NAD⁺/NADH ratio could result in tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle and ETC arrest, as well as other profound biochemical alterations (see Birsoy et al., 2015; Sullivan et al., 2015). Therefore, it could be argued that the loss of responsiveness to hypoxia in embryonic Ndufs2-deficient glomus cells is the result of a generalized disruption of mitochondrial homeostasis rather than a specific consequence of MCI dysfunction. In addition, how mitochondrial ROS production is acutely modulated by physiological hypoxia in O₂sensitive cells remains a subject of debate (Michelakis et al., 2004; Waypa et al., 2010; McElroy and Chandel, 2017). To address these fundamental questions, we explored the mechanisms of acute O₂ sensing in adult mice after inducible Ndufs2 deletion and chemical regeneration of NAD⁺ as an electron acceptor. We also investigated the compartmentalization of mitochondrial ROS production during hypoxia, as well as the acute effect of succinate dehydrogenase modulation on O₂ sensing. Our results strongly suggest that a high reduced coenzyme Q/coenzyme Q ratio (CoQH₂/CoQ) and the subsequent production of mitochondrial ROS at the rotenone-sensitive MCI Q-site are essential for acute responsiveness to hypoxia.

RESULTS

Loss of Systemic and Cellular Responsiveness to Acute Hypoxia Parallels Inhibition of MCI Function

In this study we used animals carrying Ndufs2 floxed/– alleles and ubiquitously expressing tamoxifen (TMX)inducible CRE recombinase (ESR-NDUFS2 mice) (Fernández-Aguera et al., 2015). Experiments were performed on 4monthold mice, 7–8 weeks after the onset of TMX treatment (TMX-containing diet for 4 weeks; see inset in Figure 1A) and 1–2 weeks before the

animals died due to generalized loss of MCI function. Wildtype mice (with floxed and wildtype alleles without CRE and treated with TMX) exhibited normal acute ventilatory responses to hypoxia and hypercapnia as monitored by plethysmography. However, in TMX-treated ESR-NDUFS2 mice the HVR was practically abolished, whereas the response to hypercapnia remained unaltered (Figures S1A–S1C). The loss of the HVR after TMX treatment was gradual (Figures 1A–1D) and occurred in parallel with the decrease in MCI (NADH/ubiquinone oxidoreductase) activity (Figures 1E and S1D). The ESR-NDUFS2 mice had histologically normal CBs (see Fernández-Aguera et al., 2015), although the responsiveness to acute hypoxia of single CB chemoreceptor cells from these mice was greatly impaired. The neurosecretory responses to hypoxia, recorded by amperometry from *Ndufs2*-deficient glomus cells in CB slices (Figure S1E), disappeared with a time course similar to that of the inhibition of MCI activity (see Figures 1E and 1F). Moreover, the rise in cytosolic $[Ca^{2+}]$ induced by hypoxia, a characteristic response of Fura2-loaded glomus cells, was almost completely abolished in inducible *Ndufs2*-null cells, although they responded to other stimuli (high K^+ , hypercapnia and hypoglycemia) (Figures 1G–1J). Inducible adult *Ndufs2* deficient glomus cells had a normal resting membrane potential and input resistance as well as basal cytosolic Ca^{2+} levels and catecholamine secretion rate (see Figure S2A), thereby distinguishing them from embryonic *Ndufs2*-null cells, which exhibited a 5fold increase in input resistance and 15 mV resting depolarization compared with controls (Fernández-Aguera et al., 2015). Small changes in some electrophysiological parameters with respect to controls (Figures S2B–S2E) did not seem to affect the cell responses to hypercapnia and hypoglycemia (Figure 1J). Together, these data indicate that inhibition of MCI activity secondary to *Ndufs2* ablation in adult mice results in a selective loss of responsiveness to acute hypoxia by chemoreceptor CB cells. Other essential morphological, biophysical, and functional properties of CB cells from ESR-NDUFS2 mice remained unchanged, therefore ruling out the unlikely possibility that the loss of complex I activity in all tissues could have nonspecific indirect effects on the glomus cells.

Inducible *Ndufs2* Deficiency Inhibits MCI Signaling under Hypoxia

We next studied the effect of inducible *Ndufs2* ablation on the cellular levels of NADH and ROS. Control (wildtype) cells showed the typical reversible and graded increases in NAD(P)H autofluorescence evoked by different levels of hypoxia (Figures S3A and S3B) (Buckler and

Turner, 2013). These responses were practically abolished in cells from ESR-NDUFS2 mice (Figures 2A–2C), which showed a sustained increase in their basal NAD(P)H level with respect to controls (discontinuous line, Figure 2A, top). However, this value (1.6fold) was much smaller than the one estimated in embryonic *Ndufs2*-deficient cells (2.7fold) obtained from TH-NDUFS2 mice (Fernández-Aguera et al., 2015)(Figure 2D) (see below). Rotenone elicited a marked rise in NAD(P)H, which was also drastically reduced in *Ndufs2*-deficient cells (Figures S3C–S3E). In parallel with the NAD(P)H changes, hypoxia induced a reversible increase in glomus cell mitochondrial ROS, which we measured with a redox-sensitive fluorescent protein probe (ro-GFP) that was genetically targeted to the intermembrane space (IMS) (Waypa et al., 2010; Fernández-Aguera et al., 2015)(Figures 2E–2G and S4A–S4C). Similar to the NAD(P)H signal (see Figure S3B), the IMS ROS signal showed the hyperbolic dose-dependent relationship (Figures 2E and 2H) characteristic of CB responses to hypoxia (see López-Barneo et al., 2016) and was also strongly inhibited in inducible *Ndufs2*-null glomus cells (Figures 2E–2G). Although most of the *Ndufs2*-deficient cells were unresponsive to hypoxia (Figure 2E, third trace), 45% of them showed a measurable response, but with approximately half the amplitude of the response recorded in control (wildtype) cells (Figures 2E, fourth trace, and 2G) (see Discussion). However, the small ROS signals seen in cells from ESR-NDUFS2 mice were unable to induce a cellular response (elevation of cytosolic Ca²⁺ or transmitter release) during exposure to low PO₂ (see Figures 1 and S1). The basal level of oxidation, as determined using ro-GFP targeted to the cytosol, was virtually normal in inducible *Ndufs2*-null glomus cells (Figures 2I and 2J). In contrast, this parameter increased >3fold in CB cells from embryonic TH-NDUFS2 mice (Fernández-Aguera et al., 2015). These data indicate that inducible *Ndufs2*-deficient cells exhibit strong inhibition of MCI signaling (NADH and ROS production) during acute hypoxia, thereby explaining the unresponsiveness to hypoxia of ESR-NDUFS2 mice (see Figure 1).

Contrasting Effects of Hypoxia on ROS Production in Mitochondrial Compartments: Influence of *Ndufs2* Deficiency

As mitochondria can generate ROS at various sites along the ETC (see Murphy, 2009; Brand et al., 2016), we investigated the possible source of ROS produced during hypoxia in glomus cells. The IMS ROS measurements described in the previous section were complemented with experiments in which the ROS protein sensor was genetically targeted to the mitochondrial matrix.

In sharp contrast with the hypoxia-induced ROS increases observed in the IMS and cytosol (Figures 2E–2H; see also Fernández-Aguera et al., 2015), lowering the PO₂ produced a highly reproducible, reversible, and dose-dependent decrease in ROS at the mitochondrial matrix, although the probe was highly sensitive to exogenous H₂O₂ and mito-paraquat, an agent that selectively generates superoxide within the mitochondrial matrix (Robb et al., 2015)(Figures 3A, top, 3B, 3C, and S4D–S4F). These differential ROS responses to hypoxia were repeatedly seen in separate slices from the same CB that were transfected with the ro-GFP probe targeted to either the mitochondrial IMS or the matrix (Figure 3D). To further rule out nonselective changes in the probe targeted to the matrix, we tested that its sensitivity to oxidation with small concentrations of H₂O₂ was the same in cells maintained in normoxia or hypoxia (Figures S4G–S4I). Interestingly, the decrease in matrix ROS in response to lowering PO₂ was not abolished in either inducible *Ndufs2*-deficient glomus cells (Figure 3A, bottom, 3B, and 3C) or in cells from embryonic TH-*NDUFS2* mice (Figure S5). In agreement with this finding, blockade of MCI with rotenone produced an increase in ROS in both the IMS and the matrix, and in most cells a strong occlusion of any further effect of hypoxia on the intermembrane ROS levels. However, rotenone did not prevent the decrease in ROS production observed in the matrix during hypoxia (Figures 3E and 3F). In some cells, rotenone (R1 mM) induced ROS in the IMS even decreased during exposure to hypoxia (Figures S6A and 3F). In these cells it was possible that the hypoxia-dependent MCI ROS production was completely blocked and the signal at the IMS reflected rotenone-induced ROS changes in the matrix. This finding provides a satisfactory mechanistic explanation for the decrease in rotenone-induced secretion by lowering PO₂, a phenomenon repeatedly observed in mouse (Figure S6B, top) and rat (Ortega-Sáenz et al., 2003; García-Fernández et al., 2007)(Figure S6B, bottom) glomus cells. The decrease of spontaneously or rotenone-induced matrix ROS during exposure to hypoxia was confirmed using mitoNeoD, a mitochondria-targeted superoxide probe (Shchepinova et al., 2017)(Figures S4J–S4L). These unprecedented data demonstrate, in real time, opposite reversible changes in glomus cell mitochondrial ROS in the matrix and IMS during physiological hypoxia (see Discussion). Importantly, the inhibition of matrix ROS production by hypoxia (secondary to the decrease in O₂ available for superoxide production) in *Ndufs2*-deficient cells indicates that their mitochondria are metabolically functional, and are capable of producing ROS in an O₂dependent manner.

Responsiveness to Acute Hypoxia and Chemical Regeneration of Electron Acceptors

The experimental evidence provided in the previous sections suggests that the abolition of responsiveness to hypoxia in *Ndufs2*-deficient cells from ESR-NDUFS2 mice is not the result of mitochondrial arrest secondary to NADH or ROS accumulation, but that it is specifically related to the lack of MCI function. To gather further support for this concept, we treated glomus cells with pyruvate and aketobutyrate (aKB), which are converted, respectively, to lactate or ahydroxybutyrate (aHB) (Figure 4A). These reactions, catalyzed by enzymes (lactate dehydrogenase and bhydroxybutyrate dehydrogenase) expressed in CB cells (see Gao et al., 2017b), consume NADH and regenerate the NAD⁺ required for the function of dehydrogenases in the TCA cycle (Sullivan et al., 2015). As expected, pyruvate and aKB produced a rapid decrease in NADH levels in glomus cells, which was more pronounced in *Ndufs2*-null cells (with high basal NADH levels) than in control cells (Figures 4B–4D). The hypoxic NADH signal had approximately the same amplitude in controls and cells treated with pyruvate (which can regenerate NAD⁺ but also provide acetyl CoA to the TCA cycle) but it was reduced in amplitude in cells treated with aKB, which sequesters NADH by converting it to the nonmetabolizable aHB (Figures 4B and 4E) (Sullivan et al., 2015). The hypoxic NADH signal in both embryonic and inducible *Ndfus2*deficient glomus cells (TH-NDUFS2 and ESR-NDUFS2 mice, respectively) remained abolished even after exposure to pyruvate or aKB (Figures 4D and 4E).

To further stimulate regeneration of electron acceptors (an increase in the NAD⁺/NADH ratio) in *Ndufs2*-deficient cells, we cultured glomus cells and CB slices for >12 hr with either pyruvate (10 mM) or aKB (2.5 mM). Following these treatments, chronically treated cells from wildtype mice were, similar to controls, systematically responsive to hypoxia (Figures S7A and S7B). Chronic exposure to 2.5 mM aKB, a protocol used in subsequent experiments, did not seem to cause a significant change in the electrophysiology of the glomus cells, as they maintained a constant resting potential (control: -43.7 ± 1.3 mV, $n = 15$; treated with 2.5 mM aKB: -43.4 ± 2.3 mV, $n = 7$), input resistance (control: 3.3 ± 0.2 GU, $n = 19$; treated with 2.5 mM aKB: 3.2 ± 0.3 GU, $n = 11$) and amplitude of voltage-dependent K⁺ current measured at -10 mV (control: 273 ± 26 pA, $n = 28$; treated with 2.5 mM aKB: 272 ± 26 pA, $n = 12$). As observed in the acute treatments (see Figure 4), the amplitude of the NADH signal induced by hypoxia in cells incubated overnight with aKB was smaller than in controls due to NADH sequestration (Figures S7A and S7C). Cells (wildtype and *Ndufs2* deficient) that were chronically treated with aKB showed a clear decrease in their basal NADH level. This was particularly evident in inducible *Ndufs2*-null glomus cells

(from ESR-NDUFS2 mice), in which the NADH levels were even lower than those in wildtype cells without aKB treatment (dashed line in Figure 5A). However, even with low basal NADH levels, cells with a dysfunctional MCI exhibited complete abolition of the reversible NADH increase induced by hypoxia. Unresponsiveness to hypoxia was maintained after incubation of these cells with dimethyl succinate to favor respiration through MCII (Figures 5B and 5C). Similar to the NADH signal, the mitochondrial IMS ROS signal induced by hypoxia (see Figure 2) remained markedly inhibited in inducible *Ndufs2*-null glomus cells incubated with aKB in the presence or absence of dimethyl succinate (Figures 5D–5G). In accordance with these findings, the hypoxic rise in cytosolic Ca^{2+} , which was abolished in inducible *Ndufs2*-deficient cells (Figure 1), was not rescued by the aKB and dimethyl succinate treatments. However, the response to hypercapnia or high K^{+} in these cells remained only slightly altered (Figures 5H–5J). These findings further support the view that MCI activity is essential for acute O_2 sensing by peripheral chemoreceptors and that, in MCI-deficient cells, the regeneration of electron acceptors and exogenous administration of permeable MCII substrates (dimethyl succinate) do not reactivate responsiveness to hypoxia.

Acute Oxygen Sensing Is Reversibly Modulated by Transient Modification of Succinate Dehydrogenase Activity

The model of acute O_2 sensing based on the accumulation of reduced ubiquinone (CoQH_2) during hypoxia (Figure 6A; also see Discussion), predicts that the O_2 responsiveness of glomus cells should be highly sensitive to acute changes in succinate dehydrogenase activity. To provide support for this concept, we treated glomus cells from wildtype mice with dimethyl malonate (DMM), a membrane-permeable competitive inhibitor of succinate dehydrogenase (see Chouchani et al., 2014). Exposure of glomus cells to DMM caused a reversible inhibition of the hypoxia-induced NADH (Figures 6B and 6C) and IMS ROS (Figures S7D and S7E) signals. Given that DMM induced small changes in fluorescence of unknown origin in some cells, we also performed experiments on CB slices to monitor the responsiveness to hypoxia by amperometry (see Figure S1E). DMM treatment for only a few minutes was sufficient to produce a significant decrease in the magnitude of the secretory response to hypoxia, which was fully reversible after DMM washout (Figures 6D and 6E). The opposite effects were observed in cells exposed to dimethyl succinate, which increased the response to hypoxia, presumably due to the increase in CoQH_2

production by MCI (Figures 6F–6H). Therefore, these data strongly suggest that a high CoQH₂/CoQ ratio is essential to set the sensitivity of glomus cells to changes in PO₂ (see Discussion).

DISCUSSION

Acute O₂ Sensing Depends on MCI Function

Genetic deletion of *Ndufs2* (a component of the ubiquinone/rotenone binding site) in mouse cells prevents MCI assembly and abolishes MCI enzymatic activity, leaving a functional MCIIMCIV pathway (see Fernández-Aguera et al., 2015). Here, we have shown that inducible *Ndufs2* ablation in adult mice produces the progressive disappearance of the acute systemic HVR and abolition of the secretory response to hypoxia in CB glomus cells in parallel with the loss of NADH/ubiquinone oxidoreductase activity. We have also demonstrated complete inhibition of the rise in cytosolic [Ca²⁺] induced by lowering PO₂ in *Ndufs2*-null glomus cells. The abolition of the responses to hypoxia (rise in cytosolic [Ca²⁺] and catecholamine release) in these glomus cells occurred while they maintained normal responses to hypercapnia and hypoglycemia. Unlike cells from embryonic TH-NDUFS2 mice (Fernández-Aguera et al., 2015), the inducible *Ndufs2*-deficient glomus cells exhibited a basal level of cytosolic ROS similar to that of control (wildtype) cells. The levels of reduced pyridine nucleotides in conditional *Ndufs2*-deficient glomus cells were high (in comparison with controls), although they reached lower values than those recorded in cells with embryonic *Ndufs2* deletion. In addition, inducible *Ndufs2*-deficient glomus cells had similar biophysical parameters (input resistance and resting membrane potential) to control cells. These observations argue against a generalized metabolic alteration in CB cells from inducible MCI-deficient (ESR-NDUFS2) mice and strongly suggest that they are able to repurpose metabolism to compensate for the inhibition of NADH/ubiquinone oxidoreductase activity. In the metabolically adapted inducible *Ndufs2*-deficient cells, the dose-dependent hypoxia-induced NADH and ROS signals were markedly inhibited, thereby explaining the lack of global responsiveness of these cells to hypoxia.

The use of non-glycolytic pyruvate and its conversion to lactate may be one of several alternative metabolic routes by which MCI-deficient glomus cells regenerate NAD⁺ in order to maintain mitochondrial metabolism and the ETC. To rescue *Ndufs2*-null cells from potential mitochondrial inhibition (Birsoy et al., 2015; Sullivan et al., 2015), we performed experiments with cells

incubated in the presence of exogenous pyruvate and aKB to regenerate NAD⁺. aKB was demonstrated to sequester NADH with high efficiency due to its conversion to nonmetabolizable aHB (Sullivan et al., 2015). In these conditions of active NAD⁺ regeneration, both embryonic and inducible Ndufs2-deficient glomus cells exhibited almost complete unresponsiveness to hypoxia, even in the presence of exogenous membrane-permeable dimethyl succinate to bolster the MCIIMCIV pathway. Taken together, these data strongly suggest an essential physiological role of MCI-derived NADH and ROS in acute O₂ sensing.

Compartmentalization of Mitochondrial ROS Production during Hypoxia

Mitochondria are the major source of cellular ROS, which can have deleterious effects on cell integrity and survival (Liu et al., 2002; Quinlan et al., 2013). However, controlled ROS production by mitochondria can also serve fundamental physiological functions (Sena and Chandel, 2012). We have previously shown that the resting membrane K⁺ channels in CB glomus cells are inhibited by intracellular application of H₂O₂ (Fernández-Aguera et al., 2015); therefore, ROS production during exposure to hypoxia can mediate cell depolarization. However, whether mitochondrial ROS increase or decrease during hypoxia and the physiologically relevant site(s) of ROS production remain matters of debate (Archer et al., 1993; Michelakis et al., 2004; Murphy, 2009; Waypa et al., 2010; Brand et al., 2016). We have provided evidence of highly reproducible opposite acute changes in ROS during hypoxia in CB glomus cell mitochondria: an increase in the IMS and a decrease in the matrix. Similar qualitative responses have been reported in cultured vascular smooth muscle, although in these cells (which are less O₂ sensitive than glomus cells) the changes in ROS were only appreciable during sustained hypoxia (1.5% O₂ for 10–30 min) and reversibility was not demonstrated (Waypa et al., 2010). In CB glomus cells, highly reversible ROS changes occur within the first minute after exposure to hypoxia, with a time course and dependence on PO₂ levels similar to that of the global cellular responses (rise in cytosolic [Ca²⁺] and catecholamine release) to decreasing PO₂ (see López-Barneo et al., 2016). Taken together, these data indicate a subcellular compartmentalization of ROS production during hypoxia in the O₂sensitive glomus cells. They also may help explain the contrasting results on hypoxic mitochondrial ROS production in O₂sensitive smooth muscle cells classically reported by In our glomus cell preparation, rotenone increased ROS production in the mitochondrial IMS and matrix and occluded any further hypoxia-induced increase in intermembrane ROS, but it did not prevent the hypoxic inhibition of matrix

ROS. Rotenone is known to block the ubiquinone-binding site (Q-site) and generate ROS in the peripheral arm of MCI due to backlog of electrons onto the FMN site (F-site) and upstream dehydrogenases (for a detailed review see Murphy, 2009; Brand et al., 2016; see also schemes in Figures 7A and 7B). Therefore, our findings, which are in full agreement with the selective occlusion of responsiveness of glomus cells to hypoxia by rotenone (Ortega-Sáenz et al., 2003; García-Fernández et al., 2007), strongly suggest that hypoxia-induced MCI ROS are generated at the Q-site. Here, the increase in the CoQH₂/CoQ ratio induced by hypoxia may lead to slow down of electron flux in MCI (slow down ET in Figure 7C). This would result in an increased lifetime of the reduced form of the N₂ Fe/S cluster (due to the low availability of nonreduced ubiquinone), electron leak, and the production of superoxide anions (O₂⁻). It could be speculated that negatively charged O₂⁻ are electrostatically repelled by the negative potential in the mitochondrial interior and directly channeled to the IMS, thereby being undetectable in the matrix (see Figure 7C). In support of this proposal, the hypoxic increase in ROS in the IMS was strongly inhibited in Ndufs2-deficient cells, whereas the hypoxic inhibition of matrix ROS, a manifestation of the decrease in O₂ available to generate superoxide, was unaffected. The residual hypoxic IMS ROS signal seen in inducible Ndufs2-null glomus cells could be due to incomplete washout of the NDUFS2 protein after TMX treatment or result from the production of ROS at other mitochondrial sites during hypoxia. A decrease in O₂ reduction at MCIV after lowering the PO₂ would produce an upstream backlog of electrons and could therefore lead to the generation of superoxide in MCII or MCIII (Liu et al., 2002; Waypa et al., 2010). Indeed, an increase in IMS ROS produced by MCIII appears to be important for pulmonary artery hypoxic vasoconstriction (Waypa et al., 2013). In glomus cells, however, the contribution of ROS produced outside MCI to acute hypoxia signaling seems to be negligible, as the hypoxic IMS ROS signal is strongly inhibited by rotenone or genetic MCI dysfunction (Ndufs2 deficiency), even in the presence of MCII substrates (dimethyl succinate) or regenerated NAD⁺. Moreover, under these conditions the responsiveness of glomus cells to hypoxia is selectively and completely abolished.

Succinate Dehydrogenase Activity, Coenzyme Q Redox Status, and Acute Responsiveness to Hypoxia of Peripheral Chemoreceptor Cells

MCI-deficient CB glomus cells can survive and maintain most of their functional properties (Fernández-Aguera et al., 2015); in contrast, genetic inhibition of MCII results in marked cell

death in the CB (Díaz-Castro et al., 2012). Acutely O₂-sensitive CB cells have several metabolic specifications, which include unusually high levels of anaplerotic pyruvate carboxylase and biotin, which are necessary to produce oxaloacetate, thereby replenishing TCA cycle intermediates (see Ortega-Sáenz et al., 2016; Gao et al., 2017b). In addition, CB cells contain high levels of succinate in comparison with other neural tissues (Fernández-Aguera et al., 2015). It seems, therefore, that glomus cells may have an active metabolism that results in a high CoQH₂/CoQ ratio (see Fernández-Aguera et al., 2015; Gao et al., 2017b). It is known that in mitochondria with a succinate-dependent abundant electron supply and high CoQH₂ levels combined with high electromotive force, reverse electron transport (RET) can occur at the MCI, leading to a burst of ROS and the reduction of NAD⁺ to NADH at the FMN site (Krishnamoorthy and Hinkle, 1988; Pryde and Hirst, 2011; Chouchani et al., 2014; for a detailed review see Murphy, 2009). RET is known to be blocked by rotenone (Lambert and Brand, 2004; Orr et al., 2013). Therefore, in CB glomus cells with a high CoQH₂/CoQ ratio in normoxia, a further increase in CoQH₂ during hypoxia could lead to leak of electrons at the ubiquinone-binding site due either to slow down of electron transfer from the N₂ iron/sulfur cluster to ubiquinone (black line in Figure 7C) or even to RET (blue line in Figure 7C) if CoQH₂ levels reach sufficiently high values. Any of these circumstances would lead to MCI ROS production and NADH accumulation to signal ion channels (see Figure 7C) (Gao et al., 2017a). In addition to the evidence discussed in this section, strong support for this model is provided by the fast and reversible modulation of glomus cell responsiveness to hypoxia by inhibition (DMM) or activation (dimethyl succinate) of succinate dehydrogenase reported here (see Figures 6, S7D, and S7E). It is important to keep in mind that glomus cells are highly specialized cells, with distinct metabolic features and mitochondrial functions, which allowed us to record unprecedentedly fast and reversible ROS changes during exposure to hypoxia. In this way, the time course and compartmentalization of the mitochondrial ROS signals recorded from glomus cells may not be representative of the behavior of other cell types that are unresponsive to acute hypoxia.

The data provided in this paper indicate that the CoQ redox status, a parameter that links mitochondrial ETC and metabolism, plays a fundamental role in setting the responsiveness to hypoxia of acutely O₂-sensing glomus cells. Interestingly, succinate-dependent high CoQH₂ levels and RET have been shown to participate in several relevant pathophysiological processes, such as postischemic damage to the heart (Chouchani et al., 2014) and the switching to proinflammatory

phenotype in macrophages (Tannahill et al., 2013; Mills et al., 2016). Moreover, the level of reduced ubiquinone can also act as a sensor to finely tune the stability of mitochondrial supercomplexes in variable metabolic conditions of cells (Guara's et al., 2016). In this context, acute O₂ sensing by CB chemoreceptor cells must be viewed as the result of the coupling of a highly sensitive mitochondrial ETC and metabolism to membrane ion channel activity, which has evolved for homeostatic adaptation to changes in external and internal milieu.

Limitations of Study

Our study has been performed in adult CB cells that exhibit a selective loss of responsiveness to acute hypoxia in parallel with the inducible genetic abolition of MCI function. Although we have shown that these MCI-deficient glomus cells survive well and have functional mitochondria, a remote possibility is that the metabolic disruption caused by the lack of MCI may have contributed to the altered sensitivity of these cells to changes in O₂ tension. We show that responsiveness to hypoxia was not recovered by treating the cells with pyruvate or aKB (to regenerate NAD⁺), or after their incubation with MCII substrates (dimethyl succinate). Further support for the role of MCI in acute O₂ sensing will come from experiments in mouse models with an assembled MCI containing selective mutations at the ubiquinone-binding site. Another useful model to prevent major metabolic alteration secondary to mitochondrial dysfunction may be overexpression of the yeast single subunit NADH-quinone oxidoreductase (NDI1) in MCI-deficient glomus cells. A limitation inherent to our study derives from the small size of the CB, which prevents detailed molecular analyses from being performed. We have tried to overcome this limitation by microfluorimetrically measuring several parameters (cytosolic Ca²⁺, NADH, and ROS) in single cells. In this regard, significant advances may be at hand in the future as new microfluorimetric techniques to measure other cell parameters (e.g., reduced quinone or ATP levels) are developed.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

I.A.M., P.G.R., H.T.T., L.G., M.C.F.A., V.B.H., and P.O.S. performed the experiments. I.A.M., P.G.R., H.T.T., L.G., P.O.S., and J.L.B. designed the study and contributed to generating the draft of the manuscript. J.L.B. coordinated the project and the writing of the paper.

DECLARATION OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing interests.

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KEY RESOURCES TABLE

REAGENT or RESOURCE	SOURCE	IDENTIFIER
Bacterial and Virus Strains		
VQAd ro-GFP	ViraQuest	Cat#111414
VQAd CMV GDP- roGFP	ViraQuest	Cat#022411
VQAd CMV mito-roGFP	ViraQuest	Cat#122909
Chemicals, Peptides, and Recombinant Proteins		
MitoNeoD	Laboratory of M. Murphy (Shchepinova et al., 2017)	N/A
MitoPQ	abcam	Cat#146819
Fura 2 AM	TefLabs	Cat#0103
Rotenone	SIGMA	Cat#R-8875
Dimethyl malonate	SIGMA	Cat#136441
Dimethyl succinate	SIGMA	Cat#W239607
Sodium 2-oxobutyrate (α KB)	SIGMA	Cat#K-0875
Sodium pyruvate	SIGMA	Cat#P-5280
Collagenase II	SIGMA	Cat#C-6885
Trypsin	SIGMA	Cat#T-8003
Porcine elastase	Calbiochem	Cat#324682
Critical Commercial Assays		
Complex I enzyme activity dipstick assay kit	abcam	Cat#ab109720
Bio-Rad protein assay	BioRad	Cat#500-0006
Experimental Models: Organisms/Strains		
Mouse: ESR-NDUFS2 (B6/129SV background)	Laboratory of José López-Barneo (Femández-Agüera et al., 2015)	N/A
Mouse: TH-NDUFS2 (B6/129SV background)	Laboratory of José López-Barneo (Femández-Agüera et al., 2015)	N/A
Primary cultures: Carotid body slices	Laboratory of José López-Barneo (Femández-Agüera et al., 2015)	N/A
Primary cultures: Dispersed glomus cells	Laboratory of José López-Barneo (Femández-Agüera et al., 2015)	N/A
Software and Algorithms		
ImageQuant TL	GE Healthcare	N/A

CONTACT FOR REAGENT AND RESOURCE SHARING

Further information and requests for reagents should be directed to and will be fulfilled by the Lead Contact, Jose' López-Barneo(lbarneo@us.es).

EXPERIMENTAL MODEL AND SUBJECT DETAILS

Animals

Mice were housed at regulated temperature ($22\text{C}\pm 1\text{C}$) in a 12 hr light/dark cycle with ad libitum access to food and drink. TH-NDUFS2 and ESR-NDUFS2 mice were previously generated by our group ([Fernández-Aguera et al., 2015](#)). Both male and female mice were used in the current study; these animals were on a mixed B6/129SV background. Two month old ESR-NDUFS2 mice were treated with a tamoxifen-containing diet (TAM400/CreER, 400 mg tamoxifen citrate/kg, Harlan

Laboratories) for one month followed by 34 weeks of normal diet prior to experiments. The mice were sacrificed by intraperitoneal administration of a lethal dose of sodium thiopental (120150 mg/kg) before tissue dissection. All procedures were approved by the Institutional Committee of the University of Seville for Animal Care and Use (2012PI/LB02 and 220915332). Handling of the animals was conducted in accordance with the European Community Council directives 86/609/EEC, and 2010/63/EU for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals.

Preparation of Carotid Body Slices and Dispersed Cells

CB slices were prepared for amperometric and microfluorimetric recordings, as described previously (Ortega-Sáenz et al., 2010, 2018; Muñoz-Cabello et al., 2018). Carotid bifurcations were rapidly extracted and the CBs were removed and bathed on a Tyrode 0Ca^{2+} solution containing (in mM): 148 NaCl, 2 KCl, 3 MgCl₂, 10 HEPES, 10 glucose, pH 7.4 at 4°C. The CBs were then included in 1% (w/v) low melting point agarose in PBS, which were sectioned at 150 μm with a vibratome (VT1000S, Leyca) in cold Tyrode 0Ca^{2+} solution. CB slices were treated with an enzymatic solution (PBS pH 7.4 supplemented with 50 mM CaCl₂ (Sigma), 0.6 mg/mL collagenase II (Sigma), 0.27 mg/mL trypsin (Sigma) and 1.25 U/mL porcine elastase (Calbiochem)) for 5 min at 37°C. After digestion, the CB slices were cultured in DMEM (0 glucose)/DMEMF12 (GIBCO) medium (3:1) supplemented with 100 U/mL penicillin (BioWhittaker), 10 mg/mL streptomycin (BioWhittaker), 2 mM L-glutamine (BioWhittaker), 10% fetal bovine serum (Gibco), 84 U/L insulin (Actrapid), and 1.2 U/mL erythropoietin at 37°C in a 5% CO₂ and 21% O₂ incubator for 24-48 hr prior to use.

CB cell dispersion and culture were performed as described previously by our laboratory for microfluorimetric recordings and patch-clamp experiments (Ortega-Sáenz et al., 2010; Muñoz-Cabello et al., 2018). Dissected CBs were incubated in an enzymatic solution (PBS pH 7.4 supplemented with 50 mM CaCl₂ (Sigma), 0.6 mg/mL collagenase II [Sigma], 0.27 mg/mL trypsin (Sigma) and 1.25 U/mL porcine elastase [Calbiochem]) for 20 min at 37°C. Then, CBs were mechanically dissociated by stretching with needles and incubated at 37°C for 5 min. Finally, cells were mechanically dispersed by pipetting and plated on glass cover slips treated with poly-L-lysine and kept in culture medium (DMEM (0 glucose)/DMEMF12 (Gibco) medium (1:1) supplemented with 100 U/mL penicillin (BioWhittaker), 10 mg/mL streptomycin (BioWhittaker), 2 mM

L-glutamine (BioWhittaker), 10% fetal bovine serum (Gibco), 84 U/L insulin (Actrapid). CB cells were maintained at 37°C in a 5% CO₂ and 21% O₂ incubator for 24 hr.

METHOD DETAILS

Plethysmography

To assess ventilatory function, awake unrestricted mice were placed inside plethysmography chambers (EMKA Technologies) as previously described (Ortega-Sáenz et al., 2018). The chambers were constantly perfused with normal air (21% O₂, normoxia), 10% O₂ (hypoxia), or 5% CO₂ (hypercapnia). The experimental protocol consisted of two cycles of normoxia/5 min hypoxia/normoxia followed by a cycle of normoxia/2 min hypercapnia/normoxia. The O₂ and CO₂ tensions and breathing frequency were continuously monitored and recorded in each experiment.

Measurement of Mitochondrial Complex I Activity

Mitochondria were isolated from mouse kidneys and the maximum MCI enzymatic activity was measured with a spectrophotometer as previously described with minor modifications (see Díaz-Castro et al., 2012; Fernández-Aguera et al., 2015 and references therein). Mitochondria were freeze-thawed 3 times in order to disrupt the membrane. Ten to 20 mg of the resulting submitochondrial particles were used to estimate NADH:ubiquinone oxidoreductase MCI activity, which was determined by measuring the rotenone-sensitive decrease in absorbance at 340 nm due to NADH oxidation at 30°C. MCI activity was normalized with the protein amount, as determined by Bradford assay (BioRad).

MCI activity in the superior cervical ganglion (SCG) was determined using an enzyme activity dipstick assay kit (abcam) (see Fernández-Aguera et al., 2015). Four independent measurements were performed, each one using SCGs pooled from 5 mice. SCGs were homogenized in 100 µl extraction buffer followed by incubation on ice for 20 min. The homogenate was then centrifuged at 16,000 g for 30 min and the supernatant was collected for the enzymatic assay. Five µg of protein extract, which was determined using the BioRad protein assay (BioRad), were applied to measure the MCI activity. The signals on the dipstick were scanned with an image analyzer (ImageQuant LAS 4000mini, GE Healthcare) and their intensity was quantified using the ImageQuant TL software (GE Healthcare).

Amperometric Recording of Single Cell Catecholamine Secretion in Slices

Catecholamine secretion from glomus cells in CB slices was performed as described previously from our laboratory (Ortega-Sáenz et al., 2010, 2018). To test responsiveness to hypoxia, hypercapnia or hypoglycemia, slices which had been incubated overnight in culture medium were transferred to a recording chamber and continuously perfused with a control solution containing (in mM): 117 NaCl, 4.5 KCl, 23 NaHCO₃, 1 MgCl₂, 2.5 CaCl₂, 5 glucose and 5 sucrose, at 35—C. In 40 mM K⁺ solution, NaCl was replaced equimolarly with KCl. The "normoxic" solution was bubbled with a gas mixture of 20% O₂, 5% CO₂, and 75% N₂ (O₂ tension 145 mmHg). The "hypoxic" solution was bubbled with 5% CO₂, and 95% N₂ to reach an O₂ tension of 10 to 15 mmHg in the chamber. The "hypercapnic" solution was bubbled with 20% CO₂, 20% O₂ and 60% N₂. For the 0 mM glucose experiments all glucose in the external medium was replaced with sucrose. Pyruvate and aketobutyrate (aKB) were added to the external solution at the indicated concentrations. In succinate and malonate experiments, 5 mM of dimethyl succinate or dimethyl malonate was added, respectively, to the control solution. Osmolality of solutions was 300 mOsm/kg and the pH 7.4. Secretory events were recorded with a 10 mm carbonfiber electrode. Amperometric currents were recorded with an EPC8 patch-clamp amplifier (HEKA Electronics, Lambrecht/Pfaltz, Germany), filtered at 100 Hz and digitized at 250 Hz before storage on computer. Data acquisition and analysis were performed with an ITC16 interface (Instrutech Corporation, NY, USA) and PULSE/PULSEFIT software (HEKA Electronics). The secretion rate (femtocoulombs (fC)/min) was calculated as the amount of charge transferred to the recording electrode during a given period of time. The cumulative secretion signal was the sum of the time integral of successive amperometric events.

Ca²⁺, NAD(P)H, and ROS Measurements Using Microfluorimetric Techniques

Intracellular Ca²⁺, NAD(P)H, and ROS were determined by microfluorimetry in single dispersed glomus cells (Ca²⁺ and NADH) or cells in CB slices (mitochondrial ROS production) following previously described methods (Fernández-Aguera et al., 2015; Shchepinova et al., 2017). The recording system consists of an inverted microscope (Nikon eclipse Ti) equipped with a 40x/0.60 NA objective and a filter wheel, a monochromator (Polychrome V, Till Photonics), and a CCD camera, controlled by Aquacosmos software (Hamamatsu Photonics). The recording solution and the gas compositions to regulate O₂ level were the same as described above for amperometric

analysis. In the acute experiments, 10 mM pyruvate, 2.5 mM aKB, 4 mM of dimethyl succinate, or 5 mM dimethyl malonate was added to the control solution for recording. In the chronic experiments, the drugs were added to the culture medium, and after overnight incubation, the recordings were performed as the acute experiments.

For the cytosolic Ca²⁺ measurements, cultured CB cells plated on coverslips were incubated with a loading medium (4 mM Fura2AM; TefLabs MW 1002) in DMEM without serum at 37C for 30 min under dark condition. Then, the loading medium was replaced by complete culture medium to remove extra Fura2AM and cells were further incubated for 15 min. For the experiments, a coverslip was transferred to the recording chamber (z0.2 mL) with a continuous flow of solution, which was bubbled with a mixture of gases to obtain the desired O₂ tension. The acquisition protocol was established at the beginning of the experiment using Aquacosmos software. For Fura2AM recordings, a spatial resolution of 4x4 pixels, an excitation time of 20 ms and an acquisition interval of 2 seconds were selected. Fura2AM has two fluorescence excitation peaks at approximately 340 and 380 nm, with emission at 510 nm, which allows to perform ratiometric recordings. A dichroic FF409Di03 (Semrock) and a band pass filter FF01510/84 (Semrock) were used. Background correction was performed by subtracting the fluorescent signal of a cellfree region from the intensity of the regions of interest (ROI) selected for the experiment.

NAD(P)H microfluorimetric measurements were performed in CB dispersed cells using a non-ratiometric protocol. NAD(P)H autofluorescence has an excitation peak at 360 nm and emits at 460 nm. Coverslips with CB cells were transferred to the recording chamber and continuously perfused with external solution as indicated before. An acquisition protocol was designed with a spatial resolution of 4x4 pixels, an excitation time of 150 ms ($\lambda = 360$ nm), and an acquisition interval of 5 s. A dichroic FF409Di03 (Semrock) and a band pass filter FF01510/84 (Semrock) were used. Background fluorescence was subtracted in all the experiments.

To measure ROS production, redox-sensitive green fluorescent protein (ro-GFP) probes were used, which were targeted to either the mitochondrial intermembrane space (IMS), mitochondrial matrix, or the cytosol (Waypa et al., 2010). CB slices were incubated in complete culture medium supplemented with 2 mL ro-GFP construction incorporated in an adenoviral vector (ViraQuest Inc, North Liberty, Iowa). Different ro-GFP constructs were used to target to specific subcellular compartments: cytoro-GFP (VQAd ro-GFP), IMSro-GFP (VQAd CMV GDPro-GFP) y matrixro-

GFP (VQAd CMV mitoro-GFP). After overnight incubation with the adenoviral vectors, CB slices were maintained in the culture medium without ro-GFP construct for 24 hr. For the experiments a CB slice was transferred to the recording chamber and bathed with solution with variable O₂ tension. A dichroic Di02R488 (Semrock) and a band pass filter FF01520/35 (Semrock) were used for the experiments. Ro-GFPs have two fluorescence excitation peaks at 400 and 484 nm, with emission at 535 nm, which allow the ratiometric measurements and to examine reversible changes of the redox state. To study the basal redox state, glomus cells were treated with 1 mM dithiothreitol to achieve maximum reduction and 0.1 mM H₂O₂ for maximum oxidation.

To measure superoxide (O₂⁻) production within the mitochondrial matrix of dispersed mouse glomus cells we performed realtime measurements in a confocal fluorescence microscopy setup (Nikon A1R+). MitoNeoD was synthesized and stabilized with sodium borodeuteride as described (Shchepinova et al., 2017). Stock solution was dissolved in DMSO, bubbled with nitrogen to remove any oxygen, and aliquoted in a nitrogen atmosphere to maintain the MitoNeoD in its reduced form (pale green). For the experiments, dispersed glomus cells plated on coverslips were incubated in complete medium containing 5 mM MitoNeoD for 30 to 40 min in the incubator. Then coverslips were washed with complete medium and transferred to the microscope chamber and perfused with control solution. During the experiment superoxide was produced and MitoNeoD was oxidized to MitoNeoOH, the formation of which was detected by confocal microscopy. MitoNeoOH was excited with a laser at 561 nm wavelength and the emission was recorded in the interval between 564 and 606 nm. Images were taken every 5 s to detect online small changes in spontaneous superoxide production in response to hypoxia or rotenone (5 mM) plus hypoxia. Experiments were performed at 37°C.

Patch Clamp Recordings in Dispersed Carotid Body Glomus Cells

The electrophysiological properties of CB glomus cells were studied using the patch-clamp technique. The membrane potential was estimated in cells under current-clamp conditions. The holding and macroscopic currents were recorded from dispersed mouse glomus cells using either the perforated patch or the whole cell configurations as adapted in our laboratory (Ortega-Sáenz et al., 2010; Muñoz-Cabello et al., 2018). Patch clamp pipettes (24 MU) are pulled from capillary glass tubes (Kimax, Kimble Products) with a horizontal pipette puller (Sutter instruments model P1000) and firepolished with a microforge MF830 (Narishige). Voltage-clamp recordings were

obtained with an EPC7 amplifier (HEKA Elektronik). The signal was filtered (310 kHz), subsequently digitized with an analog/digital converter (ITC16 Instrutech Corporation) and finally sent to the computer. Data acquisition and storage was performed using the Pulse/pulsefit software (Heka, Elektronik) at a sampling interval of 20 ms. Data analysis was performed using the Igor Pro Carbon (Wavemetrics) and Pulse/pulsefit (HEKA Elektronik) programs. All experiments were conducted at 30C-33C. Macroscopic Ca²⁺, Na⁺, and K⁺ currents were recorded in dialyzed glomus cells. Solutions used to record whole-cell Na⁺ and Ca²⁺ currents contained (in mM): external solution: 140 NaCl, 10 BaCl₂, 2.5 KCl, 10 HEPES, and 10 glucose, pH 7.4 and osmolality 300 mOsm/kg; and internal solution: 110 CsCl, 30 CsF, 10 EGTA, 10 HEPES, and 4 ATPMg, pH 7.2 and osmolality 285 mOsm/kg. The external solution used to record whole-cell K⁺ currents was the same control solution used for amperometric analysis and the internal solution contained (in mM): 80 K⁺ glutamate, 50 KCl, 1 MgCl₂, 10 HEPES, 4 MgATP, and 5 EGTA, pH 7.2. Experiments designed to estimate the cell's resting potential and to measure the inward holding current were carried out using perforated patches with 240 mg/mL amphotericin B added to the pipette solution, which contained (in mM): 70 K₂SO₄, 30 KCl, 2 MgCl₂, 1 EGTA, 10 HEPES, pH 7.2. The standard bath solution contained (in mM): 117 NaCl, 4.5 KCl, 23 NaHCO₃, 1 MgCl₂, 2.5 CaCl₂, 5 glucose, and 5 sucrose, pH 7.4. For chronic aKB experiments, the cells were incubated with 2.5 mM aKB overnight at 37C in a 5% CO₂ incubator. The electrophysiological experiments were done using the same solutions mentioned above supplemented with 2.5 mM aKB.

QUANTIFICATION AND STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Unless otherwise specified, the data are presented as mean ± SEM with the number (n) of experiments indicated. Normality was tested with the Shapiro-Wilk test. When necessary, a log transformation was performed to normalize the distribution prior to parametric analyses. Data from two groups were analyzed with either a t test or a paired t test. Data with multiple groups were analyzed by ANOVA or RMANOVA followed by a posthoc Tukey's test. For data without a normal distribution, nonparametric tests (Mann-Whitney rank sum test or ANOVA on ranks followed by a posthoc Tukey's test) were performed. Statistical analyses were performed using SigmaPlot (12.0). A $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Main Figures and Figure legends

Figure 1. Loss of Systemic and Cellular Responsiveness to Acute Hypoxia Parallels Inhibition of MCI Function in ESR-NDUFS2 Mice

(A–C) Inset. Time course of tamoxifen (TMX) treatment in ESR-NDUFS2 mice. Representative plethysmographic recordings of changes in breathing frequency during hypoxia (10% O₂) in wildtype (blue) and ESR-NDUFS2 (green) mice before (A), and 4–7 days (B), or 21–28 days (C) after TMX treatment. (D–F) Time-dependent decrease in the systemic hypoxic ventilatory response (D) (n = 7–10/group), MCI activity measured in kidney (E) (n = 5/group), and hypoxia-induced catecholamine secretion rate in carotid body slices (F) (n = 7–16 recordings from 4 to 7 mice/group) of ESR-NDUFS2 mice compared with their wildtype littermates before (PreTMX) and after (PostTMX) TMX treatment. ESR-NDUFS2 mice before TMX treatment had only one functional allele of *Ndufs2*. *p < 0.05 compared with wildtype, **p < 0.001 compared with wildtype, \$p < 0.05 compared with 4–7 days PostTMX.

Figure 2. Inducible Ndufs2 Deficiency Inhibits MCI Signaling Under Hypoxia in Carotid Body Glomus Cells

(A) Hypoxia-induced changes in NAD(P)H autofluorescence recorded in glomus cells from wildtype and ESR-NDUFS2 mice. The green discontinuous line in the upper panel indicates the basal NAD(P)H level in Ndufs2-deficient cells.

- (B) Percentage of cells with a hypoxia-induced increase in NAD(P)H autofluorescence from wildtype (blue, n = 59/12 cells/mice) and ESR-NDUFS2 (green, n = 34/4 cells/mice) mice. Note that none of the Ndufs2-deficient cells tested (n = 34) responded to hypoxia.
- (C) Quantification of the hypoxia-induced increase in NAD(P)H autofluorescence from responsive glomus cells of wildtype (n = 51/12 cells/mice) and ESR-NDUFS2 (n = 0/4 cells/mice) mice.
- (D) Average basal NAD(P)H autofluorescence in glomus cells from wildtype, ESR-NDUFS2, and TH-NDUFS2 mice (n = 59/12, 34/4, 60/5 cells/mice, respectively).
- (E) Representative recordings of changes in ROS in the mitochondrial intermembrane space (IMS) induced by hypoxia and 0.1 mM H₂O₂ in control (from wildtype mice) (two separate recordings at the top) and Ndufs2-deficient (two separate recordings at the bottom) glomus cells. Note in the two top recordings that the (F) Percentage of glomus cells that exhibited a hypoxia-induced increase in IMS ROS from wildtype (blue, n = 54/10 cells/mice) and ESR-NDUFS2 (green n = 29/7 cells/mice) mice.
- (G) Quantification of the hypoxia-induced increase in IMS ROS from hypoxia-responsive glomus cells from wildtype (n = 47/10 cells/mice) and ESR-NDUFS2 (n = 14/7 cells/mice) mice.
- (H) Quantitative relationship between the amplitude of the IMS ROS signal (ordinate) and the level of hypoxia (abscissa) in mouse glomus cells. PO₂ levels: basal (145 mmHg; n = 12/6 cells/mice); 45 mmHg (n = 6/3 cells/mice); 27.5 mmHg (n = 12/6 cells/mice); and 12.5 mmHg (n = 12/6 cells/mice). The hyperbolelike curve was fitted by eye.
- (I) Changes in cytosolic ROS in glomus cells from wildtype and ESR-NDUFS2 mice transfected with cytosolic ro-GFP (Cytoro-GFP) in the presence of 1 mM DTT and 0.1 mM H₂O₂.
- (J) Level of cytosolic oxidation (percentage of oxidized Cytoro-GFP) in glomus cells from wildtype (blue, n = 20/3 cells/mice) and ESR-NDUFS2 (green, n = 16/3 cells/mice) mice.

Figure 3. Compartmentalization of Acute Hypoxia-Induced Mitochondrial ROS and Differential Effects of Ndufs2 Deficiency

(A) Representative recordings of changes in ROS in the mitochondrial matrix induced by hypoxia (H) and 0.1 mM H₂O₂ in control (wildtype, top) and Ndufs2-deficient (bottom) glomus cells. (B) Percentage of glomus cells that exhibited a hypoxia-induced decrease in mitochondrial matrix ROS in wildtype (blue, n = 89/8 cells/mice) and ESR-NDUFS2 (green, n = 46/5 cells/mice) animals.

(C) Box diagram showing the quantification of the mitochondrial matrix decrease in ROS recorded in hypoxia-responsive glomus cells from wildtype (n = 81/8 cells/mice) and ESR-NDUFS2 (n = 37/5 cells/mice) mice.

(D) Representative recordings of the hypoxia-induced increase in ROS in the mitochondrial IMS (left) and the decrease in matrix ROS (right) obtained in slices of the same wildtype carotid body.

(E and F) Representative recordings and corresponding quantification (box diagram) of the reversible changes in IMS (E) (top) and matrix (E) (bottom) ROS from glomus cells in response to hypoxia and MCI inhibitor (1–5 mM rotenone [rot]) (IMS: hypoxia, n = 16/6 cells/mice; hypoxia + rot, n = 16/6 cells/mice; matrix: hypoxia, n = 15/4 cells/mice; hypoxia + rot, n = 7/3 cells/mice).

Figure 4. Acute Regeneration of NAD⁺ and Responsiveness to Hypoxia of Glomus Cells from WildType and Ndufs2-null Mice

- (A) Enzymatic reactions of pyruvate and aketobutyrate (aKB)dependent NAD⁺ regeneration.
- (B) Representative recordings illustrating the fast decrease in basal NAD(P)H levels after the addition of 10 mM pyruvate (left) and 2.5 mM aKB (right) to cultured glomus cells from wildtype mice. Note that the reversible increase in NAD(P)H fluorescence in response to hypoxia was maintained in both cases. a.u., arbitrary units.
- (C) Quantification of the decrease in basal NAD(P)H levels after the addition of pyruvate (10 mM) and aKB (2.5 mM) to cultured glomus cells from wildtype (n = 20/6 cells/mice and n = 18/6 cells/mice, respectively), ESR-NDUFS2 (n = 20/3 cells/mice and n = 19/3 cells/mice, respectively), and TH-NDUFS2 (n = 43/3 cells/mice and n = 44/3 cells/mice, respectively).
- (D) Representative recordings illustrating the fast decrease in basal NAD(P)H levels after application of 2.5 mM aKB in isolated glomus cells from ESR-NDUFS2 (left) and TH-NDUFS2 (right) mice. Note that the response to hypoxia was not restored after aKB-induced NAD⁺ regeneration.
- (E) Quantification of the increase in NAD(P)H levels in glomus cells exposed to acute hypoxia and bathed in the control solution (wildtype, n = 51/12 cell/mice; ESR-NDUFS2, n = 34/4 cells/mice, TH-NDUFS2, n = 60/5 cells/mice), a solution containing 10 mM pyruvate (wildtype, n = 20/6 cells/mice; ESR-NDUFS2, n = 20/ 3 cells/mice; TH-NDUFS2, n = 43/3 cells/mice) or a solution containing 2.5 mM aKB (wildtype, n = 15/6 cells/mice; ESR-NDUFS2, n = 19/3 cells/mice; TH-NDUFS2, n = 44/3 cells/mice).

**p < 0.001. In (C) and (E) data are represented as mean ± SEM.

Figure 5. Loss of Responsiveness to Hypoxia by Inducible Ndufs2-deficient Glomus Cells Is Not Restored by Maintained Chemical NAD⁺ Regeneration and Incubation with High Levels of Succinate

ESR-NDUFS2, n = 34/4 cells/mice; TH-NDUFS2, n = 60/5 cells/mice) or in solution containing 2.5 mM α KB (wildtype, n = 17/3 cells/mice; ESR-NDUFS2, n = 12/3 cells/mice; TH-NDUFS2, n = 22/3 cells/mice). Note that the NAD(P)H levels in the cells from ESR-NDUFS2 mice incubated in 2.5 mM α KB (discontinuous line) were below the levels measured in cells from wildtype mice incubated with the control solution. Data in control solution (the same as in Figure 2A) are shown for comparison.

(B) Representative recordings of changes in NAD(P)H autofluorescence induced by hypoxia in glomus cells from ESR-NDUFS2 mice after overnight incubation with 2.5 mM aKB (left) or 2.5 mM aKB + 5 mM dimethyl succinate (DMSuc) (right).

(C) Percentage of cells that exhibited a hypoxia-induced increase in NAD(P)H autofluorescence in glomus cells from wildtype mice (blue, n = 59/12 cells/mice) and ESR-NDUFS2 mice (green) incubated in control solution (n = 34/4 cells/mice), solution containing 2.5 mM aKB (n = 12/3 cells/mice), or solution containing 2.5 mM aKB + 5 mM DMSuc (n = 19/3 cells/mice).

(F) Percentage of glomus cells from wildtype mice that exhibited an hypoxia-induced increase in IMS ROS incubated in control solution (blue, n = 54/10 cells/mice) and percentage of responsive glomus cells from ESR-NDUFS2 mice (green) incubated in control solution (n = 29/7 cells/mice) in solution containing aKB (n = 26/4 cells/mice) or in solution containing aKB + DMSuc (n = 28/3 cells/mice).

(D and E) Representative recordings of hypoxia-induced ROS changes in the mitochondrial IMS in glomus cells from ESR-NDUFS2 mice incubated overnight with 2.5 mM aKB (D) or 2.5 mM aKB + 5 mM DMSuc (E).

Figure 6. Modulation of Glomus Cell Responsiveness to Hypoxia by Transient Modification of Succinate Dehydrogenase Activity

(A) Scheme illustrating the increase in reduced ubiquinone (CoQH₂) during exposure to hypoxia and the subsequent accumulation of ROS and NADH in MCI.

(B) Representative recording illustrating the NADH changes in dispersed glomus cells during exposure to hypoxia (H). The hypoxic NADH signal is reversibly decreased in amplitude by acute application of succinate dehydrogenase inhibitor (5 mM dimethyl malonate, DMM).

(C) Box diagram showing the quantification of the increase in NADH fluorescence during hypoxia (n = 38–43 cells from 5 mice/group).

(D) Top: amperometric recording illustrating the secretory response to hypoxia of glomus cells in carotid body slices. The hypoxic secretory signal was reversibly inhibited by acute application of 5 mM DMM. Bottom: the cumulative secretion signal calculated as the time integral of the amperometric recording.

(E) The average secretion rates induced by hypoxia (control and DMM, n = 8 recordings from 4 animals; recovery, after DMM washout, n = 5 recordings from 3 animals).

*p < 0.05. In (E) and (H), data are represented as mean ± SEM.

(F) A typical amperometric recording, demonstrating the enhancement of the hypoxia-induced glomus cell secretory response in slices treated with 5 mM DMSuc.

(G) Illustration of the increase in secretion rate induced by hypoxia in control versus DMSuc in 10 independent experiments. Note the logarithmic scale in the ordinate.

(H) The average secretion rate during hypoxia in control or DMSuc-treated glomus cells (n = 10 recordings from 7 animals/group).

Figure 7. MCI Signaling in Response to Rotenone Blockade or Acute Hypoxia

Note that the ROS potentially generated in MCII or MCIII are omitted in the scheme. ET, electron transport; RET, reverse electron transport. See text for detailed explanation.

Supplemental Information

Acute O₂ Sensing: Role of Coenzyme QH₂/Q Ratio and Mitochondrial ROS Compartmentalization

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Whole animal plethysmography

Mitochondrial complex I activity (SCG)

Glomus cell secretory activity in slices

Figure S1

Figure S1. Related to Figure 1. Selective Decrease in Systemic and Glomus Cell Responsiveness to Acute Hypoxia in ESR-NDUFS2 Mice

(A) Representative plethysmographic recording of changes in breathing frequency during hypoxia (~10% O₂) and hypercapnia (5% CO₂) in wild-type mice (4 months old, 1 month after termination of Tamoxifen treatment) compared to ESR-NDUFS2 (B) littermates. (C) Quantification of breathing frequencies during exposure to Normoxia, Hypoxia, and Hypercapnia of wild-type mice (n = 6) and ESR-NDUFS2 mice (n = 10). *p<0.05. (D) Mitochondrial complex I (MCI) activity in the superior cervical ganglion (SCG) of wild-type and ESR-NDUFS2 mice (n=4 replicates from 5 mice each) determined using a dipstick assay. (E) Representative amperometric recordings of catecholamine release from glomus cells in carotid body slices from wild-type and ESR-NDUFS2 mice exposed to hypoxia (PO₂ = 10 to 15 mm Hg), 20% CO₂, and 40 mM KCl. Inset: Schematic drawing of quantal dopamine release from a glomus cell recorded with the amperometric technique. In C and D data are represented as mean ± SEM.

Electrical and basal parameters in glomus cells

A

	Whole-cell		Perforated patch	
	WILD-TYPE	ESR-NDUFS2	WILD-TYPE	ESR-NDUFS2
Cell capacitance (pF)	2.06 ± 0.08 (32)	1.82 ± 0.06* (33)	-	-
Input resistance (GOhm)	-	-	3.22 ± 0.24 (18)	3.15 ± 0.20 (18)
Membrane potential (mV)	-	-	-43.67 ± 1.33 (15)	-43.87 ± 0.17 (23)
	WILD-TYPE	ESR-NDUFS2		
Basal cytosolic [Ca ²⁺] wavelength ratio (a.u)	0.35 ± 0.08 (62)	0.32 ± 0.01 (53)		
Basal catecholamine secretion (fC/min)	54 ± 26 (11)	18 ± 11 (7)		

Voltage-dependent ionic currents in glomus cells

B

C

D

E

Figure S2

Figure S2. Related to Figure 1 and 2. Electrophysiological Properties and Basal Cell Parameters of Carotid Body Glomus Cells from Wild Type and ESR-NDUFS2 Mice

(A) Top. Electrophysiological parameters of glomus cells (number in parentheses) from wild-type and ESR-NDUFS2 mice. Cells were recorded either with the whole-cell configuration of the patch clamp technique (whole-cell) or with the perforated patch technique. Bottom. Values of basal cytosolic Ca^{2+} and catecholamine secretion rate in wild-type and *Ndufs2*-deficient cells. (B) Representative recordings of K^+ currents in whole-cell patch clamped glomus cells from wild-type and ESR-NDUFS2 mice. Depolarizing (50 ms) voltage steps between -30 and +50 mV were applied from a holding potential of -70 mV. (C) Average peak K^+ current density versus membrane potential relationship obtained from wild-type (blue) and ESR-NDUFS2 (green) glomus cells (n= 18 cells from 9 mice and 16 cells from 8 mice, respectively). (D) Representative macroscopic Ca^{2+} and Na^+ currents recorded in glomus cells from wild-type and ESR-NDUFS2 mice. Depolarizing (10 ms) voltage steps (to -40 and -20 mV) were applied from a holding potential of -70 mV. (E) Average peak Ca^{2+} current density versus membrane potential relationship measured in glomus cells obtained from wild-type (blue; n= 17 cells from 8 mice) and ESR-NDUFS2 (green; 18 cells from 9 mice) animals. * $p < 0.05$. Note the small changes in capacitance (an electrical parameter that is proportional to cell size) (A) and the amplitude of peak voltage-dependent K^+ (C) and Ca^{2+} (E) currents in *Ndufs2*-deficient cells with respect to controls. These changes did not seem to affect the cell responses to hypercapnia and hypoglycemia (see Fig. 1J).

NAD(P)H responses to hypoxia and rotenone

Figure S3

Figure S3. Related to Figure 2. Graded NADH Responses to Various Levels of Oxygen Tension (PO₂) and Inhibition of Rotenone-Induced NADH Accumulation in *Ndufs2*-Deficient Glomus Cells.

(A) Graded changes in NAD(P)H autofluorescence recorded in glomus cells from wild-type mice during exposure to hypoxia (PO₂, ~12.5 mm Hg) and 3% O₂ (PO₂, ~27.5 mm) in the recording chamber. (B) Quantitative relationship between the amplitude of the NAD(P)H signals (ordinate) and the level of hypoxia (abscissa) in mouse glomus cells. PO₂ levels: Basal (145 mmHg; n = 46/13 cells/mice); 90 mm Hg (12% O₂, n = 10/2 cells/mice), 45 mm Hg (6% O₂, n = 16/2 cells/mice); 27.5 mm Hg (3% O₂, n = 45/13 cells/mice); 12.5 mm Hg (solution bubbled with N₂, n = 46/13 cells/ mice). The hyperbole-like curve was fitted by eye. (C) NAD(P)H signals induced by hypoxia and rotenone (1 μM) in glomus cells from wild-type (top) and ESR-NDUFS2 (bottom) mice. (D) Percentage of cells with an hypoxia- or rotenone-induced increase in NAD(P)H autofluorescence from wild-type (blue, n = 13/6 cells/mice) and ESR-NDUFS2 (green, n = 24/6 cells/mice) mice. (E). Quantification of the hypoxia- or rotenone-induced increase in NAD(P)H autofluorescence from responsive glomus cells. Wild-type: hypoxia (n = 17/6 cells/mice), rotenone (n = 12/6 cells/mice); ESR-NDUFS2: hypoxia (n = 7/6 cells/mice), rotenone (n = 11/6 cells/mice). a.u. arbitrary units. *p<0.05; **p<0.001.

Mitochondrial intermembrane space ROS-roGFP

Mitochondrial matrix ROS-roGFP

MitoNeoD

Figure S4

Figure S4. Related to Figure 3. Graded Decrease in Mitochondrial Matrix Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) in Response to Hypoxia in Glomus Cells and Monitoring of Hypoxia and Oxidant-Induced Changes in ROS Production with Different Probes.

(A) Changes in mitochondrial intermembrane space (IMS) ROS induced by small concentrations (1 and 5 μM) of H_2O_2 in cells that were maintained in normoxia ($\text{PO}_2=145$ mm Hg) and hypoxia ($\text{PO}_2 \sim 15$ mm Hg). (B) Peak amplitude of the IMS ROS signals in the two experimental conditions (Normoxia: 1 μM H_2O_2 , $n = 10/3$; 5 μM H_2O_2 , $n = 15/4$ cells/mice. Hypoxia: 1 μM H_2O_2 , $n = 7/3$; 5 μM H_2O_2 , $n = 13/5$ cells/mice). (C) Time to reach half of the maximal amplitude ($t_{1/2}$) of the IMS ROS signal induced by 5 μM H_2O_2 in cells maintained in normoxia and hypoxia (Normoxia: $n = 14/4$, Hypoxia: $n = 13/5$ cells/mice). The similarity of the signals indicates that the sensitivity of the probe targeted to the IMS was not significantly affected. (D) Representative recordings of graded changes in ROS in the mitochondrial matrix of a glomus cell induced by hypoxia (H, $\text{PO}_2 \sim 15$ mm Hg in the recording chamber) and 3% O_2 (~ 30 mm Hg in the recording chamber). The response of the same cell to application of a large (0.1 mM) H_2O_2 pulse is shown on the right of the panel. (E) Quantification of the decrease in ROS levels in the mitochondrial matrix during exposure of glomus cells to hypoxia (~ 15 mm Hg; $n = 8/2$ cells/mice) or 3% O_2 (~ 30 mm Hg; $n = 8/2$ cells/mice). $**p < 0.001$. (F) Representative recording of changes in matrix ROS induced by hypoxia (H) and mitoParaquat (mitoPQ). (G) Changes in matrix ROS induced by small concentrations (1 and 5 μM) of H_2O_2 in cells that were maintained in normoxia ($\text{PO}_2=145$ mm Hg) and hypoxia (~ 15 mm Hg). (H) Peak amplitude of the ROS signals in the two experimental conditions (Normoxia: 1 μM H_2O_2 , $n = 11/3$; 5 μM H_2O_2 , $n = 25/5$ cells/mice. Hypoxia: 1 μM H_2O_2 , $n = 14/3$; 5 μM H_2O_2 , $n = 19/3$ cells/mice). (I) Time to reach half of the maximal amplitude ($t_{1/2}$) of the matrix ROS signal induced by 5 μM H_2O_2 in cells maintained in normoxia and hypoxia (Normoxia: $n = 25/5$, Hypoxia: $n = 19/3$ cells/mice). The similarity of the signals indicates that the sensitivity of the probe targeted to the matrix was not significantly affected. (J) Representative fluorescent recordings from two glomus cells loaded with MitoNeoD, a superoxide-sensitive probe targeted to mitochondrial matrix, which showed

clearly different rate of ROS production. Note that in both cases application of hypoxia (H) repetitively produced a decrease of the slope, indicating a decrease in the rate of superoxide production. Changes in slope of the signal between the arrows are shown at an expanded time base in (K). Straight lines are fitted by eye. (L) Representative recording showing the increase in superoxide production induced by rotenone (5 μ M) in a glomus cell loaded with MitoNeoD and its attenuation during exposure to hypoxia (H). a.u. arbitrary units. In B, C, E, H and I data are represented as mean \pm SEM.

Figure S5

Figure S5. Related to Figure 3. Decrease in Matrix Mitochondrial Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) Production During Hypoxia in Carotid Body Glomus Cells of TH-NDUFS2 Mice.

(A) Representative recordings of changes in mitochondrial matrix ROS induced by hypoxia or 0.1 mM H₂O₂ in glomus cells from TH-NDUFS2 mice. (B) Percentage of cells with a decrease in mitochondrial matrix ROS in response to hypoxia from wild-type (n = 89/8 cells/mice) and TH-NDUFS2 (n= 25/3 cells/mice) animals. (C) Box diagram showing the quantification of the hypoxia-induced decrease in mitochondrial matrix ROS in hypoxia-responsive glomus cells from wild-type (n = 81/8 cells/mice) and TH-NDUFS2 (light brown n= 20/3 cells/mice) animals. a.u., arbitrary units.

ROS production at mitochondrial intermembrane space

Glomus cell secretory activity in slices

Figure S6

Figure S6. Related to Figure 3. Parallel Decrease of the Rotenone-Induced IMS ROS Signal and Secretory Activity During Exposure of Glomus Cells to Hypoxia.

(A) Representative recording of changes in intermembrane space (IMS) ROS in a glomus cell exposed to hypoxia (H, ~15 mm Hg) and rotenone (5 μ M). Note the decrease in rotenone-induced ROS during simultaneous exposure to hypoxia. Quantification of these data are include in the plot shown in Fig. 3F. (B, top, left) Secretory activity of a mouse glomus cell during exposure to rotenone and hypoxia. Note the decrease in catecholamine release induced by rotenone during simultaneous exposure to hypoxia. The cumulative secretion signal (red trace) illustrates the changes in secretion rate. (B, top, right) Quantitative changes in rotenone-induced secretion rate during exposure to hypoxia in 4 mouse glomus cells. (B, bottom, left) Secretory activity of a rat glomus cell during exposure to rotenone and hypoxia. Note the decrease in catecholamine release induced by rotenone during simultaneous exposure to hypoxia. The cumulative secretion signal (red trace) illustrates the changes in secretion rate. (B, bottom, right) Quantitative changes in rotenone-induced secretion rate during exposure to hypoxia in 4 rat glomus cells. Discontinuous straight lines are drawn to illustrate the changes in slope before and after exposure to hypoxia.

Pyruvate and α -ketobutyrate treatment

Succinate dehydrogenase inhibition

Figure S7

Figure S7. Related to Figure 5 and 6. Maintenance of the NADH Hypoxic Response in Carotid Body Glomus Cells of Wild Type Mice After Chronic Chemical Regeneration of Electron Acceptors (NAD⁺). Inhibition of Hypoxia-Induced IMS ROS Signals by Dimethylmalonate.

(A) Representative recordings of changes in NAD(P)H autofluorescence induced by hypoxia in wild type glomus cells incubated overnight in control solution (top), in solution containing 10 mM pyruvate (middle) or in solution containing 2.5 mM α -ketobutyrate (α KB, bottom). (B) Percentage of glomus cells that exhibited hypoxia-induced increase in NAD(P)H fluorescence. Wild-type cells chronically incubated in control solution (n = 59/12 cells/mice), in solution containing pyruvate (36/3 cells/mice), or in solution containing α KB (17/3 cells/mice). (C) Quantification of hypoxia-induced increase in NAD(P)H fluorescence in hypoxia-responsive wild-type glomus cells chronically incubated in control solution (n = 51/12 cells/mice), in solution containing pyruvate (30/3 cells/mice), or in solution containing α KB (12/3 cells/mice). (D) Representative recording illustrating the changes in IMS ROS during exposure to hypoxia (H) in glomus cells. The hypoxia-induced signal is reversibly inhibited by acute application of succinate dehydrogenase inhibitor (5 mM dimethyl malonate, DMM). (E) Quantification of the hypoxia-induced increase in IMS ROS in control conditions (n= 8/4, cells/mice) and during treatment with DMM (n= 8/4 cells/mice). a.u., arbitrary units, **p < 0.001. In C and E data are represented as mean \pm SEM.